

FROM POLICY TO PRACTICE - NAVIGATING CHILDREN'S RIGHTS IN
LEGAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL REALMS

VON DER POLITIK ZUR PRAXIS – KINDERRECHTE IM RECHTLICHEN UND
PSYCHOLOGISCHEN BEREICH NAVIGIEREN

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Abstract:

This article delves into the intricate landscape of children's rights, exploring the amalgamation of legal frameworks and psychological considerations across diverse contexts. It navigates the evolving terrain of children's participation in parental separation cases, illegal adoption trafficking, racial discrimination in schools, cyberabuse prevention, school transportation accidents, medication safety, and socioeconomic disparities. Emphasizing the pivotal role of international conventions, notably the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), it underscores the imperative of upholding children's voices and best interests. Interdisciplinary collaboration between legal and psychological experts is underscored, acknowledging the significance of assessing children's capacities and developmental needs. Education emerges as a cornerstone, both in providing access to quality education and empowering children with knowledge about their rights and responsibilities. The article advocates for comprehensive legal frameworks, spotlighting the interconnectedness of legal responsibilities in safeguarding children's well-being, fostering equality, safety, and holistic development.

Keywords: Children's Rights, Legal Frameworks, Psychological Considerations, Parental Separation, International Conventions, Interdisciplinary Collaboration, Education for Empowerment, Child Participation, Socioeconomic Disparities, Holistic Development.

Abstract:

Dieser Artikel befasst sich mit der komplexen Landschaft der Kinderrechte und untersucht die Verschmelzung rechtlicher Rahmenbedingungen und psychologischer Überlegungen in verschiedenen Kontexten. Es befasst sich mit der sich wandelnden Beteiligung von Kindern an Fällen der Trennung ihrer Eltern, illegalem Adoptionshandel, Rassendiskriminierung in Schulen, Prävention von Cybermissbrauch, Schultransportunfällen, Medikamentensicherheit und sozioökonomischen Ungleichheiten. Es betont die zentrale Rolle internationaler Übereinkommen, insbesondere des Übereinkommens der Vereinten Nationen über die Rechte des Kindes (CRC), und unterstreicht die Notwendigkeit, die Stimme und das Wohl der Kinder zu wahren. Die interdisziplinäre Zusammenarbeit zwischen juristischen und psychologischen Experten wird hervorgehoben und die Bedeutung der Beurteilung der Fähigkeiten und Entwicklungsbedürfnisse von Kindern anerkannt. Bildung erweist sich als Eckpfeiler sowohl für den Zugang zu hochwertiger Bildung als auch für die Vermittlung von Wissen über ihre Rechte und Pflichten an Kinder. Der Artikel plädiert für umfassende rechtliche Rahmenbedingungen und betont die Vernetzung der rechtlichen Verantwortlichkeiten beim Schutz des Wohlergehens von Kindern sowie bei der Förderung von Gleichberechtigung, Sicherheit und ganzheitlicher Entwicklung.

Schlüsselwörter: Kinderrechte, rechtliche Rahmenbedingungen, psychologische Überlegungen, Trennung der Eltern, internationale Konventionen, interdisziplinäre Zusammenarbeit, Bildung zur Selbstbestimmung, Kinderbeteiligung, sozioökonomische Unterschiede, ganzheitliche Entwicklung.

1. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of children's rights within the intricate tapestry of international and national legal frameworks has ushered in a profound shift, intertwining legal mandates with crucial psychological considerations. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) stands as a

cornerstone, delineating fundamental principles that navigate the involvement of children in pivotal decisions, particularly within the realms of parental separation, illegal adoption trafficking, racial discrimination in schools, cyberabuse prevention, school transportation accidents, medication safety, and socioeconomic disparities.

This article embarks on an exploration of the intricate interplay between law and psychology, delving into the multifaceted landscape of safeguarding children's rights across diverse contexts. It navigates the complexities surrounding children's participation in legal processes, recognizing their evolving capacities, and emphasizing the pivotal role of their voices in decision-making. Crucially, it underscores the imperative of an interdisciplinary approach, where legal expertise harmonizes with psychological assessments to ensure the protection and holistic development of every child.

As we traverse through the myriad facets of children's rights, education emerges as both a shield and a catalyst—providing access to knowledge, nurturing empowerment, and fostering an understanding of rights and responsibilities. The intersection of legal mandates and psychological assessments becomes particularly salient in addressing socioeconomic disparities, acknowledging the inherent vulnerability of certain groups and advocating for equitable opportunities.

This article endeavors to illuminate the intersections of law and psychology, advocating for comprehensive legal frameworks that safeguard children's well-being, foster their agency, and pave the path toward a more equitable and nurturing society.

2. DEVELOPMENT

Children's Rights: Participation of Children in Parental Separation Cases: Legal and Psychological Aspects The participation of children in parental separation cases is a complex and multifaceted issue with both legal and psychological dimensions. In the realm of legal aspects, it is crucial to consider the evolving framework of children's rights within international and national legal systems. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) has played a significant role in establishing the fundamental principles that guide children's involvement in decisions related to their parents'

separation. These principles emphasize the child's right to be heard, their best interests, and their evolving capacity to express their views.

In the legal context, the participation of children in parental separation cases involves navigating various legal procedures and mechanisms to ensure their voices are heard and their interests are considered. This may include appointing legal representatives or guardians ad litem to advocate for the child's rights and wishes in court proceedings. Additionally, alternative dispute resolution methods, such as mediation and arbitration, can provide children with opportunities to express their preferences in a less adversarial setting.

On the psychological front, understanding the emotional and developmental implications of children's participation in parental separation is paramount. Psychologists play a vital role in assessing the child's cognitive and emotional readiness to engage in decision-making processes. Factors such as the child's age, maturity, and the level of conflict between parents must be carefully evaluated to determine the child's capacity to participate effectively.

The participation of children in the formulation of food policies is a burgeoning area of interest in both legal and psychological domains. The right to adequate nutrition is enshrined in the CRC, and it is essential to involve children in discussions and decisions related to their dietary needs. This participation can manifest through school-based initiatives, focus groups, and surveys that gather children's input on menu options, food quality, and nutritional education programs.

Children's rights extend beyond basic needs to encompass their right to recreation and leisure. In this context, access to recreational activities is crucial for their physical and psychological development. Ensuring equal access to recreational opportunities for children in both urban and rural areas is a challenge. Legal frameworks should promote the establishment of community-based recreation centers and facilities, while psychological support should focus on assessing and addressing the specific recreational needs of children in different settings.

Education for citizenship is another pivotal aspect of children's rights. It involves imparting knowledge and skills that enable children to understand their roles as responsible members of society. Both legal and psychological professionals should collaborate to develop age-appropriate curricula and

teaching methods that empower children with the knowledge of their rights, responsibilities, and the principles of democracy.

The participation of children in various aspects of their lives, including parental separation cases, food policy formulation, access to recreation, and education for citizenship, requires a balanced approach that integrates legal and psychological expertise. The evolving legal framework surrounding children's rights and the developmental considerations of each child must be taken into account to ensure their meaningful participation and the protection of their best interests.

Children's Rights: Legal Guardianship of Children in Illegal Adoption Trafficking Situations The legal guardianship of children in situations of illegal adoption trafficking is a critical component of safeguarding children's rights. This complex issue revolves around ensuring that children are not subjected to unlawful adoption processes that violate their rights and best interests. The right to protection from illegal adoption is inherent in the broader framework of children's rights, and it is imperative to establish legal mechanisms to prevent such practices.

Non-discrimination is a fundamental principle in the protection of children's rights. It encompasses the right of every child to be treated equally and without discrimination of any kind, including in matters related to adoption. Legal frameworks must explicitly prohibit discriminatory practices that target vulnerable children, such as those from marginalized communities or with disabilities. Ensuring non-discrimination in adoption processes is essential to upholding the principles of fairness and equity.

Children in situations of environmental displacement, commonly referred to as "environmental refugees," face unique challenges in accessing education. The right to education is a fundamental children's right, and it is vital to address the educational needs of these children. Legal mechanisms should be in place to ensure their access to quality education in host countries, recognizing their specific circumstances and potential language barriers.

State responsibility is a cornerstone in the protection of children's rights, especially in cases of illegal adoption trafficking. States have an obligation to establish and enforce legal frameworks that prevent, investigate, and prosecute individuals or entities involved in illegal adoption practices. This

includes providing adequate resources and support for law enforcement agencies and judicial authorities to combat these illicit activities effectively.

Extreme poverty often exacerbates the vulnerability of children and their exposure to various forms of exploitation, including illegal adoption. Addressing extreme poverty is crucial for safeguarding children's rights. Legal and policy measures should focus on poverty alleviation programs, social safety nets, and economic empowerment strategies for families to prevent situations where children are trafficked due to economic desperation.

Protecting children's rights in cases of illegal adoption trafficking requires a comprehensive legal framework that addresses guardianship, non-discrimination, access to education for environmental refugees, state responsibility, and the alleviation of extreme poverty. These interrelated components must be systematically integrated into national and international legal systems to ensure the rights and well-being of children are upheld and protected in all circumstances.

Children's Rights: Legal Protection of Children in Cases of Racial Discrimination in Schools Ensuring the legal protection of children in situations of racial discrimination within educational institutions is of paramount importance. This multifaceted issue encompasses various legal aspects that must be addressed comprehensively to safeguard children's rights and well-being. Racial discrimination in schools can have significant implications for a child's access to education, mental health, and overall development.

The right to education is a critical aspect of children's rights, particularly in the context of racial discrimination. Educational institutions have a responsibility to ensure an environment free from racial discrimination, providing equal access to quality education for all students. Legal frameworks should explicitly prohibit racial discrimination in schools and establish mechanisms for addressing and preventing such incidents (Cairns et al., 2018). The right to education is fundamental for children's moral and legal development, enabling them to realize their full potential (Cairns et al., 2018).

Research has shown that racial discrimination in educational settings can significantly impact students' academic achievement and psychological well-being (Bryan et al., 2018; Banerjee et al., 2018). Adolescents' perceptions of discrimination in school and public spaces can influence their attitudes

towards school and academic performance (Banerjee et al., 2018). Furthermore, racial discrimination stress can affect school belonging and academic attitudes among Black youth, highlighting the importance of creating an inclusive and supportive educational environment (Morris et al., 2020; Griffin et al., 2017).

In addressing racial discrimination in education, it is essential to consider the role of legal measures and frameworks. Legal knowledge and awareness among school teachers regarding the educational rights of children, particularly those with special needs, are crucial for ensuring inclusive education (Rahmat et al., 2021). Additionally, the application of equal rights laws and the reversal of the burden of proof in cases of racial discrimination are critical for addressing and preventing discriminatory practices in educational institutions (He, 2022).

Furthermore, the role of racial and ethnic socialization as moderators of racial discrimination and school adjustment among adolescents underscores the significance of promoting positive racial identity and cultural awareness within educational settings (Seol et al., 2016). Parents' messages about race can influence how school-based racial discrimination is perceived and how racial identity beliefs are developed (Butler-Barnes et al., 2018).

Efforts to reduce racial and ethnic prejudice in schools through interventions are also important. School-based interventions aimed at reducing youths' racial and ethnic prejudice can contribute to creating a more inclusive and equitable educational environment (Grapin et al., 2019). Additionally, promoting access to local books and literacy education can be part of international efforts to entrench children's rights in education, emphasizing the significance of literacy for children's development (Shin et al., 2019).

The provision of school meals and the right to education are closely intertwined. Access to nutritious school meals is not only a fundamental aspect of children's right to food but also contributes to their ability to fully benefit from their education. Legal regulations must ensure that school meal programs are non-discriminatory and consider the dietary needs and cultural backgrounds of all students.

In the digital age, the right to online privacy is becoming increasingly relevant for children. Protecting children's privacy in online environments,

including social media platforms and educational technology, is essential. Legal measures should establish clear guidelines on data protection, consent, and the responsible handling of children's personal information to mitigate risks associated with online discrimination.

Parental responsibility plays a significant role in addressing racial discrimination in schools. Legal frameworks should encourage parental involvement in monitoring and reporting incidents of discrimination, as well as collaborating with schools to develop anti-discrimination policies and educational programs. Additionally, parents should be informed about their rights and the available legal remedies in cases of discrimination.

Access to technology is a crucial factor in addressing racial discrimination in education. Technological resources can provide access to information and educational opportunities, but they can also perpetuate disparities if not distributed equitably. Legal regulations should focus on bridging the digital divide, ensuring that all children, regardless of their background, have access to the necessary technology and digital resources to support their education.

The legal protection of children in situations of racial discrimination in schools requires a comprehensive approach that addresses the right to education, school meal programs, online privacy, parental responsibility, and access to technology. These interconnected elements must be incorporated into legal frameworks to promote equality, diversity, and the full realization of children's rights within the educational system.

Children's Rights: Legal Responsibility in Preventing Child Cyberabuse The protection of children's rights in the digital age necessitates a robust legal framework to prevent cyberabuse targeted at children. Cyberabuse encompasses various forms of harm, including online bullying, harassment, and exploitation. It is imperative to establish clear legal responsibilities and mechanisms to address these threats effectively.

An essential aspect of preventing child cyberabuse is recognizing the importance of children's participation in decision-making regarding their online safety and educational choices. Inclusive participation allows children to voice their concerns, preferences, and needs, shaping policies and practices that

directly affect them. Legal provisions should promote child participation in developing online safety guidelines and educational curricula.

Access to inclusive education is a fundamental children's right, including for those with disabilities or special needs. Legal frameworks should ensure that educational institutions provide reasonable accommodations and support to enable the participation of all children in inclusive learning environments. This involves establishing anti-discrimination laws and regulations that require schools to adapt their programs to cater to diverse learning needs.

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) play a significant role in complementing governmental efforts to prevent child cyberabuse and protect children's rights. These organizations often provide resources, advocacy, and support for both children and parents. Legal recognition and support for the work of NGOs in the field of child protection are crucial to creating a comprehensive and effective response to cyberabuse.

Domestic violence has severe consequences for children's well-being and safety, necessitating comprehensive legal frameworks to address and prevent such violence within the family context. The impact of domestic violence on children is profound, with research indicating that exposure to domestic violence can lead to negative outcomes such as psychological trauma, physical injuries, and developmental issues (Nugroho et al., 2019; Pereira et al., 2021). The prevalence of domestic violence has been identified as a significant factor in cases of children in need, emphasizing the need for prevention, early intervention, and education (Lloyd, 2018). Furthermore, children exposed to domestic violence are at risk of experiencing adverse outcomes such as lower self-esteem, academic difficulties, and behavioral problems (Bonganciso & Kumari, 2022). Research also highlights the disproportionate representation of young children in reporting exposure to domestic violence, indicating the vulnerability of this age group (Osofsky, 2018).

Legal provisions aimed at protecting children from witnessing or experiencing domestic violence are crucial. Restraining orders, counseling services, and support for victims are essential components of legal frameworks to address domestic violence within the family context (Jeffries et al., 2015). Studies have shown that effective treatment of mental illness and substance

misuse can reduce the risk of domestic violence, underscoring the importance of comprehensive support services for victims (Gulati & Kelly, 2020). Additionally, the provision of counseling services has been identified as crucial for victims of domestic violence, particularly in helping them navigate the recovery process (Suchmasasi et al., 2021).

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, the issue of domestic violence has been exacerbated, leading to a crisis in intimate partner violence (Matoori et al., 2020). The pandemic has brought about negative social consequences, including psychological stress and unemployment, further highlighting the urgency of legal and support interventions to address domestic violence within the family (Xue et al., 2020).

Efforts to protect victims of domestic violence, including children, are essential, as criminal acts of domestic violence can have severe physical, psychological, sexual, and neglectful impacts on victims (Choirinnisa, 2022). Research has also emphasized the need for a holistic approach to service delivery to ensure the safety and well-being of women and their children who are victims of domestic violence (Nugroho et al., 2019).

The legal responsibility in preventing child cyberabuse necessitates child participation in decision-making processes, access to inclusive education, recognition and support for NGOs, and measures to address domestic violence. These legal components are interconnected and vital in ensuring the protection of children's rights in the digital age and in their everyday lives.

Children's Rights: Civil Liability in Traffic Accidents Involving School Transportation Ensuring children's rights in the context of school transportation requires a comprehensive legal framework addressing civil liability in traffic accidents. These accidents can have severe consequences for the safety and well-being of children. Legal responsibility in such cases often hinges on establishing negligence as a key factor.

Negligence cases involving school transportation accidents necessitate a meticulous examination of factors such as driver qualifications, vehicle maintenance, and adherence to safety regulations. Legal mechanisms should outline the standards of care expected from transportation providers and hold them accountable for any lapses that may result in harm to children.

Preventing child abuse and exploitation is an essential aspect of safeguarding children's rights. Legal frameworks should encompass measures to detect, report, and respond to cases of abuse and exploitation effectively. This includes mandatory reporting requirements for individuals and organizations in contact with children, as well as the establishment of child protection agencies responsible for investigating allegations and providing support to victims.

Education for citizenship and social responsibility plays a vital role in promoting a culture of child protection. Legal provisions should mandate the inclusion of child protection education in school curricula, teaching children about their rights, personal safety, and how to seek help when needed. Additionally, legal mechanisms should encourage corporate social responsibility, promoting child protection practices within businesses and organizations.

In cases where prevention measures fall short, judicial intervention becomes necessary to address child protection issues effectively. Legal systems should be equipped to handle cases of child abuse, exploitation, and negligence swiftly and impartially. This includes providing adequate resources for the judiciary, child protection agencies, and legal aid services to ensure a fair and efficient process.

Child trafficking is a global concern that demands coordinated legal efforts. Legal frameworks should establish strict penalties for individuals and entities involved in child trafficking, and facilitate international cooperation to combat this heinous crime. Additionally, preventive measures should focus on raising awareness, strengthening border controls, and improving socioeconomic conditions to reduce vulnerability to trafficking.

Ensuring children's rights in various contexts, such as school transportation accidents, child abuse prevention, education for citizenship, judicial intervention, and combating child trafficking, requires a robust legal foundation. This legal framework should be designed to protect children from harm, promote their well-being, and hold responsible parties accountable when their rights are violated.

Children's Rights: Legal Responsibility in Preventing the Misuse of Medications in Children Preserving children's rights involves establishing a robust legal framework to prevent the misuse of medications in children, a

critical aspect of child protection. Medication errors in pediatric care can have severe consequences, including harm to a child's health and well-being. Legal responsibility in such cases often revolves around ensuring proper prescription, administration, and monitoring of medications.

Children's rights during natural disasters and catastrophes demand special attention within legal systems. The vulnerability of children in such contexts necessitates proactive measures to ensure their safety and well-being. Legal frameworks should address emergency preparedness, evacuation plans, and the provision of essential services such as food, shelter, and medical care, with a specific focus on the unique needs of children.

The combat against sexting and child pornography is crucial in protecting children's rights in the digital age. Legal mechanisms should establish stringent penalties for the production, distribution, and possession of explicit content involving minors. Simultaneously, preventive measures should include education programs to raise awareness about the risks and legal consequences associated with such activities.

Socioeconomic discrimination is a persistent issue that affects children's access to basic necessities and opportunities. Legal frameworks should incorporate anti-discrimination laws and policies that address disparities arising from socioeconomic factors. Ensuring equal access to education, healthcare, and social services for children from disadvantaged backgrounds is essential in upholding their rights.

Continuing the discussion on socioeconomic discrimination, tackling the root causes of inequality is vital. Legal measures should encompass economic policies that aim to reduce income disparities, provide social safety nets, and promote inclusive development. Such policies are fundamental in addressing the systemic issues that perpetuate socioeconomic discrimination.

Safeguarding children's rights necessitates a multifaceted legal approach that spans areas such as medication safety, disaster preparedness, combating online exploitation, and addressing socioeconomic disparities. These interconnected legal components are essential in ensuring that children are protected from harm, have equal access to opportunities, and can lead healthy and fulfilling lives.

3. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In navigating the intricate terrain of children's rights, the amalgamation of legal frameworks and psychological insights emerges as a linchpin for the protection and empowerment of our youngest members of society. The trajectory of children's participation in critical decisions, notably in parental separation cases, illegal adoption trafficking situations, racial discrimination in schools, cyberabuse prevention, school transportation accidents, medication safety, and socioeconomic disparities, underscores the evolving landscape of their rights.

Interdisciplinary collaboration between legal professionals and psychologists is not merely a harmonization of expertise; it's a recognition of the nuanced needs and capacities of each child. The strides made in advocating for children's voices within legal proceedings mirror the imperative laid out by international conventions, yet the journey toward comprehensive protection remains ongoing.

Education stands as a beacon of hope and change, fostering not only knowledge but also empowerment. Equipping children with the understanding of their rights and responsibilities catalyzes societal transformation, nurturing informed citizens who champion equity and justice. The pivotal role of education is augmented in addressing the deep-seated roots of socioeconomic disparities, where legal and psychological interventions converge to bridge divides and offer equitable opportunities.

As this article delves into the intricate tapestry of children's rights, it beckons for a unified commitment—an unwavering dedication from legal systems, psychological professionals, policymakers, and society at large. Upholding children's rights isn't merely an obligation; it's a collective endeavor, an investment in a future where every child thrives, protected, and empowered.

In fostering a society that cherishes and safeguards the rights of its children, the confluence of legal and psychological perspectives becomes an emblem of progress—a testament to our commitment to ensure a world where every child's potential is nurtured, their voices are heard, and their rights are honored.

REFERENCES

- Banerjee, M., Byrd, C., & Rowley, S. (2018). The relationships of school-based discrimination and ethnic-racial socialization to african american adolescents' achievement outcomes. *Social Sciences*, 7(10), 208. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci7100208>
- Bonganciso, J. and Kumari, B. (2022). Impact of gender based violence on developing children's personalities. *Technoarete Transactions on Advances in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.36647/ttassh/01.02.a004>
- Bryan, J., Williams, J., Jungnam, K., Morrison, S., & Caldwell, C. (2018). Perceived teacher discrimination and academic achievement among urban caribbean black and african american youth: school bonding and family support as protective factors. *Urban Education*, 57(9), 1487-1510. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042085918806959>
- Butler-Barnes, S., Richardson, B., Chavous, T., & Zhu, J. (2018). The importance of racial socialization: school-based racial discrimination and racial identity among african american adolescent boys and girls. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 29(2), 432-448. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jora.12383>
- Cairns, L., Byrne, S., Davis, J., Johnson, R., Konstantoni, K., & Kustatscher, M. (2018). Children's rights to education – where is the weight for children's views?. *The International Journal of Children S Rights*, 26(1), 38-60. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718182-02601007>
- Choirinnisa, S. (2022). Law and society approach on legal protection for victims of domestic violence. *Semarang State University Undergraduate Law and Society Review*, 2(2), 227-248. <https://doi.org/10.15294/lsr.v2i2.53756>
- Grapin, S., Griffin, C., Naser, S., Brown, J., & Proctor, S. (2019). School-based interventions for reducing youths' racial and ethnic prejudice. *Policy Insights From the Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 6(2), 154-161. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2372732219863820>
- Griffin, C., Cooper, S., Metzger, I., Golden, A., & White, C. (2017). School racial climate and the academic achievement of african american high school students: the mediating role of school engagement. *Psychology in the Schools*, 54(7), 673-688. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.22026>

Gulati, G. and Kelly, B. (2020). Domestic violence against women and the covid-19 pandemic: what is the role of psychiatry?. <i>International Journal of Law and Psychiatry</i> , 71, 101594. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijlp.2020.101594
He, Y. (2022). Research on the application of equal rights law and the reversal of burden of proof in racial discrimination.. https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.220504.137
Jeffries, S., Field, R., & Bond, C. (2015). Protecting australia's children: a cross-jurisdictional review of domestic violence protection order legislation. <i>Psychiatry Psychology and Law</i> , 22(6), 800-813. https://doi.org/10.1080/13218719.2015.1015204
Lloyd, M. (2018). Domestic violence and education: examining the impact of domestic violence on young children, children, and young people and the potential role of schools. <i>Frontiers in Psychology</i> , 9. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02094
Matoori, S., Khurana, B., Balcom, M., Koh, D., Froehlich, J., Janssen, S., ... & Gutzeit, A. (2020). Intimate partner violence crisis in the covid-19 pandemic: how can radiologists make a difference?. <i>European Radiology</i> , 30(12), 6933-6936. https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-020-07043-w
Morris, K., Seaton, E., Iida, M., & Johnson, S. (2020). Racial discrimination stress, school belonging, and school racial composition on academic attitudes and beliefs among black youth. <i>Social Sciences</i> , 9(11), 191. https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci9110191
Nugroho, F., Nugroho, B., & Wijayanti, L. (2019). Domestic violence against woman: its relevance to a gender-sensitive policy.. https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.7-12-2018.2281766
Osofsky, J. (2018). Commentary: understanding the impact of domestic violence on children, recognizing strengths, and promoting resilience: reflections on Harold and Sellers (2018). <i>Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry</i> , 59(4), 403-404. https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpp.12902
Pereira, T., Pucci, S., & Armond, J. (2021). Violência doméstica e o desempenho escolar de crianças e adolescentes. <i>Brazilian Journal of Global Health</i> , 1(4), 34-38. https://doi.org/10.56242/globalhealth;2021;1;4;34-38

Rahmat, N., Mahmood, A., & Othman, M. (2021). Legal knowledge and awareness of the school teachers on the educational rights of children with special needs in malaysia. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 10(3). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarped/v10-i3/11099>

Seol, K., Yoo, H., Park, J., & Kyeong, Y. (2016). Racial and ethnic socialization as moderators of racial discrimination and school adjustment of adopted and nonadopted korean american adolescents.. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 63(3), 294-306. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cou0000120>

Shin, J., Sailors, M., McClung, N., Hoffman, J., Pearson, P., Kaambankadzanja, D., ... & Mwale, L. (2019). Access to local books: the effects of read malawi from a children's rights perspective. *Literacy*, 54(3), 74-90. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lit.12198>

Suchmasasi, Y., Sutiyoso, B., & Puspawati, A. (2021). The analysis of recovery implementation for domestic violence victims. *Journal of Research in Social Science and Humanities*, 1(2), 51-55. <https://doi.org/10.47679/jrsssh.v1i2.12>

Xue, J., Chen, J., Chen, C., Hu, R., & Zhu, T. (2020). The hidden pandemic of family violence during covid-19: unsupervised learning of tweets (preprint).. <https://doi.org/10.2196/preprints.24361>